

ENHANCING MANDARIN CHINESE READING PROFICIENCY AMONG NATIVE ENGLISH-SPEAKING ADULT LEARNERS IN TRINIDAD AND TOBAGO THROUGH TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of technology on improving reading proficiency in Mandarin Chinese among native English-speaking adult learners in Trinidad and Tobago. Data was collected from a sample of students who had formally studied Mandarin Chinese for at least one semester at the University of the West Indies, St. Augustine campus. Participants completed two surveys and engaged in a 14-day trial using an online graded-reader website, The Chairman's Bao, designed specifically for Mandarin Chinese reading practice. Quantitative data on student performance and completion rates of readings and exercises from the website was paired with qualitative insights from learners regarding the platform's benefits and their self-reported evaluations of their reading skills before and after the trial. The findings reveal a positive relationship between the uses of a digital tool like The Chairman's Bao and enhanced reading abilities in Mandarin Chinese. Participants indicated increased engagement and perceived confidence when reading short texts entirely in simplified Chinese characters, without the use of Pinyin, a transliteration system designed to aid learners in reading characters. This study underscores the transformative potential of effectively using ICT tools in Mandarin Chinese language learning and offers valuable recommendations for regional and international educators seeking to integrate online resources into Mandarin instruction for more effective language acquisition.

Keywords: Mandarin Chinese, adult learners, technology-enhanced learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Proficiency in foreign languages is becoming an increasingly valuable skill in today's interconnected world, and Mandarin Chinese is no exception. With China's rise as a global economic and political powerhouse, the demand for Mandarin language skills has surged, particularly among English-speaking adults. These learners are often motivated by career advancement, personal satisfaction, or the desire to engage more meaningfully in global affairs. For instance, a study in New Zealand showed that self-satisfaction and career development were primary motivations for adults studying Mandarin Chinese (Wang, 2020).

However, despite this growing interest, Mandarin poses significant challenges, especially for English speakers. One of the major hurdles for English-speaking adult learners is the complexity of the Chinese writing system, which relies on logographs—symbols representing words or morphemes. Unlike English, which uses an alphabetic system, Mandarin Chinese requires learners to recognize and memorize thousands of characters, a task that can be overwhelming. The U.S. Department of State's Foreign Service Institute classifies Mandarin as a Category V language, meaning it requires extensive time and effort to

master, particularly for those accustomed to alphabetic languages (Kenny, n.d.). Studies have consistently highlighted the difficulties learners face with pronunciation, grammar, and, most notably, reading Chinese characters (Chua et al., 2020).

In this context, information and communication technology (ICT) tools present a promising avenue for addressing these challenges. The rapid growth of language learning apps, online platforms, and other digital resources has made foreign language study more accessible and flexible, which is especially important for adult learners juggling multiple responsibilities. ICT tools such as game-based apps, digital dictionaries, and interactive websites provide opportunities for learners to study at their own pace, offering solutions to time constraints that traditional classroom settings cannot. While ICT tools have shown potential in language learning, their specific effectiveness in improving Mandarin reading proficiency among English-speaking adults remains underexplored.

This research focuses on addressing the challenge of reading proficiency in Mandarin Chinese, particularly the ability to recognize and understand Chinese characters. Using an online platform, this study aims to evaluate how effectively ICT tools can support adult learners in overcoming the difficulties associated with Mandarin's logographic system. By focusing on an online reading tool called The Chairman's Bao, which offers graded news-based articles for language learners, this study will gather data on learner performance and engagement. The features on The Chairman's Bao website such as spaced repetition, multimedia resources, and gamified elements, make it a valuable tool for research into Mandarin reading proficiency.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to contribute to our understanding of how technology can enhance foreign language acquisition, especially for adult learners. Traditional methods may not fully meet the unique needs of this demographic, who require flexible, engaging, and personalized learning experiences. By examining the benefits and limitations of ICT in this context, this study seeks to provide educators and policymakers with insights into effective strategies for integrating technology into language education.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Thematic Framework: Andragogy

Understanding the unique challenges faced by adult learners and leveraging appropriate technological tools can potentially transform the landscape of language education, making it more accessible and effective. Adult learners often have distinct motivations, learning styles, and life experiences when compared to younger learners, which necessitates different instructional strategies in the classroom. Exploring these differences is quite crucial to tailoring educational approaches that maximize engagement and overall proficiency attained in language acquisition. By recognizing and addressing the specific needs of adult learners, educators can then go on to create more relevant, practical, and impactful learning experiences that facilitate better outcomes in mastering foreign languages such as Mandarin Chinese.

Andragogy, the art and science of facilitating adult learning, emphasizes the unique needs, characteristics, and learning styles of adults compared to children. Consequently, teaching adults requires distinct techniques different from the pedagogical methods used with children. This discipline assumes that the inherent differences between adults and children result in varied learning processes. One of the leading theorists in this field is the American educator Malcolm Knowles, who made significant contributions to understanding adult learning. Knowles proposed that adults are motivated to learn primarily when the learning tasks are relevant to their social roles (Merriam & Baumgartner, 2020, p. 118). Moreover, adults are driven by internal motivations rather than external ones and need to understand the rationale behind learning something (Merriam & Baumgartner, 2020, p. 119). Knowles further stated that as adults mature, their focus shifts to immediate, practical use and application of knowledge (Merriam & Baumgartner, 2020, p. 119).

Many subsequent scholars have expanded on Knowles' foundational assumptions, further exploring the dynamics of adult learning. According to Machynska and Boiko (2020), adults exhibit autonomy and self-direction in their learning approach (p. 26). They are less dependent on instructors compared to younger age groups. Furthermore, the authors emphasize an adult's wealth of knowledge attained through lived experiences, which enables them to connect new information gained with an existing experience and consciously engage in reflective learning (p. 28). Above all, adults possess an unparalleled readiness to learn when compared with young learners, who are believed to approach learning through convincing (p. 28). Adults learn for various reasons, both for personal enjoyment and with specific practical goals, which shape their educational needs.

Similar viewpoints are supported by Tardi (2021) who examined the adult learner's learning strategies in the context of acquiring a foreign language. Tardi asserts that:

Adults have metalinguistic needs higher than those of children and adolescents, greater abstracting and systematic ability, need stable rules to refer to and correlate with the structures already acquired, and require explicit reflection greater than that offered by many of the teaching materials (p. 96)

Tardi's statement underscores the need for instructional methods that are tailored to the cognitive and reflective capabilities of adult learners, ensuring that the materials used in teaching are sufficiently challenging and relevant to their individual learning needs.

Overall, the core principles of andragogy highlight the importance of creating a learning environment that respects and leverages the unique characteristics and needs of adult learners. By recognizing their autonomy, valuing their experiences, and aligning learning activities with their practical goals, educators can more effectively support adult learners in achieving their personal educational objectives.

2.2. ICT Integration in Foreign Language Study

The COVID-19 global pandemic triggered a significant shift in the education system towards online learning and the increased use of digital tools (ICT) to enhance the learning experience. This transition has highlighted the importance of integrating technology in education, facilitating remote learning, and providing new opportunities for interactive and personalized learning environments.

In foreign language education, ICT has had a profound impact, enabling immersive experiences, real-time practice, and access to diverse linguistic resources, thus significantly improving language acquisition and proficiency. The integration of ICTs in foreign language education has been extensively studied. Researchers such as Negoescu and Mitrulescu (2023) highlight how technology enables instructional content to be tailored to meet the specific needs and requirements of learners (p. 211). This customization allows students to engage with the material in ways that suit their individual learning styles, fostering a more personalized educational experience (p. 212). Moreover, the inclusion of interactive media and activities in digital learning environments, such as websites, provides students with the flexibility to explore content according to their interests and prior knowledge, thereby enhancing their engagement and learning outcomes (p. 212). Access to authentic, real-life materials through ICT further enriches the learning experience by exposing students to accurate and relevant information that mirrors real-world situations, which is crucial for developing practical language skills (p. 212).

Many studies have provided actual evidence of the efficacy of ICT in enhancing language learning. For instance, Adilbayeva et al. (2022) conducted research that demonstrated significant improvements in reading comprehension skills among students using ICT tools. The study found that the experimental group, which utilized these tools, performed better in reading comprehension tests compared to the control group (p. 27). This suggests that ICT can play a vital role in developing language learners' reading skills and contributes to a deeper understanding of foreign languages and cultures. Also, the study identified valuable websites and mobile applications that can be used to increase students' interest in learning English, broaden their perspectives, and improve their language skills (p. 28). The notion of emotioncy, as explored by Pishghadam (2015) and cited in the work of Adilbayeva et al. (2022), further supports the idea that engaging multiple senses through ICT can enhance cognitive and emotional engagement in language learning (p. 28)

Focusing specifically on the integration of ICT in Chinese language education, Huang (2022) provides insights into the effectiveness of multimedia in this context. Huang's research on teaching Chinese as a foreign language in Vietnam indicates that multimedia aids in stimulating both hemispheres of the brain by combining language with visual experiences, which enhances learning and memory retention (p. 393). The study also found that a significant majority of students perceived multimedia as essential or necessary for learning (p. 395), highlighting its importance in modern educational practices. Additionally, multimedia platforms not only improve the efficiency of teachers by providing reusable content but also help in developing students' technological competencies (p. 394). These platforms make it possible for students to improve their reading, writing, listening, and speaking abilities, as well as efficiently access and make use of online resources (p. 395). Huang's study and other related research underscore the significant impact of multimedia and ICT on forming and developing students' competencies and qualities, making them more adept at using technology to enhance their language learning experience.

Nonetheless, ICT integration may also encounter challenges, particularly in the context of Chinese language education. Zeng and Jiang (2021) identified several issues when looking at ICT integration in the Chinese

language classrooms in Australia. In their study, ten of fourteen interviewees cited "limited and blocked access" as a significant barrier, many teachers noted a lack of variety in suitable e-tools for Chinese education. (p. 21). Some educators had to create their own activities due to the unavailability of ideal applications (p. 21), while others found that the existing software and training provided by educational departments was insufficient (p. 24). Additionally, certain e-Learning platforms, such as Google Translate and YouTube, were often blocked by schools, further complicating the integration of technology (p. 21). Privacy concerns also led to the restriction of popular platforms like Kahoot, Quizz and Quizlet, limiting their use in Chinese language teaching and learning (p. 21).

Moreover, software issues such as errors, crashes, and instability were frequently reported as barriers by nine of the fourteen interviewees (Zeng & Jiang, 2021, p. 21). The cost of e-tools was another significant obstacle, with ten interviewees noting that subscription fees limited their access to full features, forcing them to rely on free or trial versions (p. 22). Additionally, the available technologies often did not align well with class time constraints, students' proficiency levels, or the Australian Curriculum requirements (p. 22).

Despite these challenges, the general, transformative potential of using ICT tools in language education remains evident. Addressing these barriers through improved software accessibility, affordability, and stability seems to further enhance the effectiveness of ICT integration in foreign language study, particularly in the Chinese context.

2.3. Reading Proficiency in Mandarin Chinese

Chinese characters present significant challenges to learners of Chinese as a second language or foreign language due to the nature and structure of characters. There are many different factors to consider when reading in Chinese characters such as the intricate strokes, syllable-character correspondence, morphological awareness, and word segmentation without inter-word spacing. Research on how adult learners acquire these skills is still relatively limited, especially compared to studies on native Chinese speakers (Zhang et al., 2023, p. 2). ICT, however, has the capability to enhance character recognition and overall reading proficiency by leveraging tools such as character recognition tests, Pinyin spelling, and mobile applications.

Studies have found that Pinyin skills, which involve phonics and phonological awareness, significantly contribute to the reading abilities of Mandarin Chinese language learners. Pinyin spelling aids in segmenting syllables into onset, rime, tone, and phonemes and reassembling them, capturing the unique linguistic features of Chinese (Xiao et al., 2020, p. 3). These skills influence reading comprehension by enhancing listening comprehension and vocabulary knowledge depth (pp. 6-7). Therefore, we can conclude that ICT tools that facilitate Pinyin spelling and provide interactive learning experiences can improve reading proficiency.

More recent studies emphasize the transformative potential of technological innovations in Chinese language education. Ou and Paciente (2024) state "virtual and augmented reality applications, immersive language learning platforms, and artificial intelligence-driven personalized learning experiences are set to revolutionize the way learners engage with Chinese texts" (p.8). They go on to further assert that interactive learning methods, which encourage active engagement and real-world application of comprehension skills, further elevate the educational experience (p. 9). Technologies like Augmented Reality (AR) combine real and virtual objects to create a unique and immersive learning experience. These tools help reduce cognitive load, facilitate interactive learning, and provide automated evaluation and feedback, supporting character recognition and reading proficiency (Li, 2023, pp. 74, 76-77). By integrating these advanced technologies and interactive methods, educators can significantly enhance reading comprehension and overall language proficiency.

3. METHODOLOGY

The sample population of this study consisted of twenty-eight (28) students ranging from ages eighteen (18) to over forty-five (45) who have studied Mandarin Chinese for at least one semester at the University of the West Indies, St. Augustine campus in Trinidad and Tobago. They all have a minimum of fifty-two (52) contact hours of formal study. As such, they were selected because, by this stage, they would be more familiar with Chinese characters. They are also likely to have developed their own learning strategies for reading and recognizing Chinese characters. Most participants in this sample population were female (89%), reflecting a slight gender-imbalance trend observed in foreign language classes in other countries such as in China (Cheng et al., 2021, p.608). To maintain anonymity, each student participant was assigned a code name

based on the Chairman's Bao website student ID uwistudent + a number (e.g. uwistudent1) This ensured that the researcher protected the individual identities of the participants throughout the study.

3.1. Research Questions

The primary hypothesis of this study is that ICT tools, like the Chairman's Bao, will significantly improve both the proficiency and confidence of adult learners in reading Mandarin Chinese. Secondary hypotheses suggest that learners with higher motivation and more positive attitudes towards technology will experience greater gains, and that completing exercises and using multimedia resources will lead to better retention and engagement. Ultimately, this research aims to identify effective ICT interventions that facilitate adult learners' journey towards Mandarin reading proficiency, helping to bridge the gap between traditional learning methods and the growing potential of technology in language education.

3.2. Data Collection

The researcher carefully selected and designed each data collection instrument listed below to gather both quantitative and qualitative data, ensuring a thorough analysis.

1. **Pre-study survey** – This initial survey was designed to gather essential demographic information and background details regarding participants' Mandarin Chinese studies.
2. **Trial on the Chairman Bao website** – This was a core stage of the research process. Participants engaged in a 14-day trial using the Chairman Bao website, a platform specifically designed to help learners improve their Mandarin Chinese reading skills. The researcher obtained written permission to use the data gathered from the Chairman Bao website directly from the website's owner. Participants were instructed to read ten beginner-level articles (HSK 1 & 2) pre-selected by the researcher without using Pinyin. The participants were also required to complete the reading comprehension exercises associated with each article. Data was collected based on participants' performance on these exercises, providing quantitative measures of their reading comprehension skills.
3. **Post-study survey** – Following the website trial, all participants in the sample completed a post-study survey consisting of both open-ended and closed questions. This survey aimed to gather feedback on their experiences using the Chairman Bao website and its perceived impact on their reading proficiency.

3.3. Research Design

Central to the research design is the self-reporting approach, which allowed participants to assess their own learning and provide insights into their firsthand experiences. This self-assessment is crucial for capturing subjective data that might not be evident through quantitative measures alone generated from the trial period on the website. The integration of self-reporting techniques throughout the surveys ensured that the study not only measured objective outcomes but also considers participants' personal perceptions, strategies and any changes in their confidence and abilities in reading Chinese characters. Given the nature of the study, the collected data was analysed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. Thematic analysis was applied to identify patterns and themes in the qualitative data, while descriptive statistics were used to summarize and interpret the quantitative data. Overall, this comprehensive and multi-faceted design provided a thorough evaluation of the Chairman Bao learning platform's impact on Mandarin Chinese reading proficiency.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1. Pre-study Survey

The data collected from the survey issued before the participants started the Chairman's Bao website trial presented a few trends about their Chinese language study, the use of ICT in foreign language study and the comfort levels with reading in Mandarin Chinese

Firstly, from the findings we can see a clear emphasis on internal motivations aligning with the principles of andragogy. Personal interest and cultural appreciation were the top motivations, with 100% and 78.5% of the participants selecting these choices, respectively. These motivations are deeply internal, reflecting a desire for personal growth and a genuine appreciation for the culture, which aligns perfectly with Knowles' assertion that adults are driven by internal motivations rather than external ones (Merriam & Baumgartner, 2020, p. 118). Additionally, travel (chosen by 53.5% of participants) and professional development (14%) were also common choices. These motivations, while somewhat external, still reflect an internal desire to enhance

one's life experiences and professional skills. These motives also indicate that adults are more focused on the immediate, practical use of the language. This practical orientation is a key principle of andragogy, emphasizing that adults learn best when they can apply new knowledge directly and immediately to their lives. This data demonstrates that adults are primarily learning Chinese not because they must, but because they want to, which enhances their engagement and commitment to the learning process.

Additionally, the data indicated an elevated level of comfort with ICT use among the participants, with the majority (78.5%) feeling comfortable (ratings 4 and 5) using technology to support their foreign language study. Notably, no respondents rated their comfort level as 1, indicating that complete discomfort with ICT is non-existent in this sample. This suggests a general readiness and openness among these adult learners to incorporate technology into their learning process. Additionally, an overwhelming majority of respondents in the sample use ICT to practice Chinese (96%). This indicates a widespread adoption of technology specifically in their Chinese language learning routines. These findings align with outcomes in Huang's 2022 study of Chinese language students in Vietnam, where the use of multimedia in language instruction was considered by their sample as beneficial. Both teachers and students emphasized the importance of multimedia in language practice, indicating that integrating technology can significantly aid in language acquisition and proficiency (p. 395). Overall, this high usage highlights the potential for technology to play a significant role in improving proficiency in a language in general or even a particular skill such as reading.

Most respondents rated their reading proficiency as very low to moderate, with no one feeling highly proficient in this skill. Confidence levels in reading without the use of Pinyin are extremely low as seen in Figure 1, with 64% of the participants rating their confidence as 1 (not confident at all) or 2 (not confident) out of 5 (very confident). On the other hand, confidence levels when reading texts in Chinese characters accompanied by Pinyin are significantly higher. In total, 61% of respondents rated their confidence level as 4 or 5 (see Figure 1). This indicates that while Pinyin serves as a valuable tool in aiding comprehension, a finding also supported by Xiao et al. (2020), an overdependence on it may not allow learners to develop full high confidence in reading a text that is solely written in characters.

Fig. 1. Pie chart A shows the confidence levels in reading Mandarin Chinese texts without Pinyin. A rating of 5 is the highest (most confident), while 1 is the lowest. No respondent gave a rating of 5. Pie chart B shows the confidence levels in reading Mandarin Chinese texts with Pinyin. A rating of 5 is the highest (most confident), while 1 is the lowest. No respondent gave a rating of 1.

4.2. The Chairman's Bao Trial

During the trial, all participants were asked to read ten articles at HSK Levels 1 and 2 and complete the accompanying reading exercises. The data gathered from the pre-study survey highlights learners' diverse expectations for this online platform to improve their Mandarin Chinese reading skills. As shown in Table 1, learners primarily aimed to build confidence, enhance vocabulary acquisition, and improve reading comprehension and speed. Additionally, many respondents valued the flexibility to study at their own convenience and pace.

Table 1 – Table showing the learners' expectations for using the Chairman's Bao learning platform to Improve Mandarin Chinese reading skills

Expectation	Number of Respondents
I expect to read Mandarin Chinese texts more quickly and efficiently	18
I expect to feel more confident in my ability to read Mandarin Chinese texts	26
I expect to study Mandarin Chinese reading at my own convenience and pace	17
I expect to learn and retain new vocabulary words	25
I expect to receive support and guidance from the platform such as explanations and tips	15
I expect to better understand the main ideas and details in Mandarin Chinese texts	19

The highest number of respondents (93%) expected to feel more confident in their ability to read Mandarin Chinese texts, indicating that confidence building is a primary goal for learners using an online platform. Overall, 89% of respondents expected to learn and retain new vocabulary words, highlighting the importance of vocabulary acquisition in their language learning journey. A considerable number of learners hoped to read texts more quickly and efficiently and better understand the main ideas and details in Mandarin Chinese texts, reflecting a desire for improved reading comprehension and speed. Furthermore, many respondents expected that through the online platform, they would be able to study at their own convenience and pace, underscoring the need for flexibility in learning schedules and the ability to tailor study sessions to individual needs.

Considering their expectations, it is important to evaluate how well the platform met these goals. The performance scores from the reading exercises provide insight into whether the learners' anticipated improvements in confidence, vocabulary acquisition, reading speed, and comprehension were realized. Below in Table 2 are the scores from the HSK Level 1 articles:

Table 2 – Table showing the test scores for the HSK 1 reading exercises.

N=28	Article 1	Article 2	Article 3	Article 4	Article 5
Mean	79.04	93.92	96.66	85.71	81.43
Mode	66.67, 86.67	100	100	100	93.33, 88.67
Standard Deviation	14.02	10.80	8.82	14.66	19.23

Based on the data collected, participants scored notably higher in Articles 2 and 3 compared to the other articles within this level. Both articles exhibited lower variability in scores, suggesting a more consistent, high level of performance. Article 3 stands out particularly, with consistently high scores and a narrower range of variability. It has the highest mean score of 96.66 and a mode score of 100, indicating that a significant proportion of participants in the sample achieved top scores. Even though Articles 4 and 5 showed strong overall performance, they both had higher standard deviations. This reflects greater variability in scores, indicating more pronounced differences in performance. Article 1, however, had the lowest mean score of 79.04, reflecting both lower average performance and greater inconsistency in scores among participants.

Table 3 – Table showing the test scores for the HSK 2 reading exercises

N=28	Article 6	Article 7	Article 8	Article 9	Article 10
Mean	82.38	84.76	78.57	83.57	82.14
Mode	93.33	93.33	93.33, 100	100	100
Standard Deviation	21.76	24.99	22.70	28.47	30.60

Based on the data collected for the HSK 2 articles (see Table 3), participants scored relatively evenly across articles 6 to 10, with mean scores ranging from 78.57 to 84.76. Article 7 had the highest mean score of 84.76, indicating better average performance compared to the other articles. Article 9 stood out with a high mean score and mode of 100, suggesting that a significant number of participants achieved top scores for this article. However, all articles showed high standard deviations, with article 10 having the highest standard deviation of 30.60. This indicates greater inconsistency in performance for Article 10. Article 8 had the lowest mean score of 78.57, reflecting slightly lower average performance compared to the other articles. Overall, the data suggests that while participants performed well across all articles, there were noticeable variances in consistency and performance levels.

Analysis of the favourite articles and their ratings reveals interesting insights into participants' preferences and perceptions. Possibly it may have influenced how the participants performed in general. Article 2 emerged as the clear favourite, receiving the highest number of votes, indicating its overall appeal. Article 3 also consistently received high ratings across all categories, being described as interesting, relevant, and inspiring by most respondents. Article 7 was another notable as the second favourite, with strong ratings for interest. Many participants performed strongly in the reading comprehension exercises. The data underscores the value of carefully selecting reading materials that resonate with adult Mandarin Chinese language learners, fostering both engagement and learning.

The completion rate of the articles offers additional insights into participants' engagement and performance. All participants completed the exercises for Articles 1 to 4, demonstrating strong engagement with these materials. Articles 5, 6, and 8 saw slightly lower completion rates at 96%, while Articles 7 and 9 had a completion rate of 93%. Article 10 had the lowest completion rate at 89%. These completion rates correlate with the interest ratings, as Article 2, the overall favourite, had a perfect completion rate, reflecting its appeal and relevance to the participants. Article 3, which also received high ratings, maintained a 100% completion rate, reinforcing its effectiveness. In contrast, Article 10, with the lowest completion rate, suggests it may not have resonated as well with the participants.

4.3. Post-study Survey

The post-study survey provided data concerning the participants' experience after using the website and how it impacted their skill level and confidence in reading texts in Chinese characters.

Most of the participants (46%) felt that their reading proficiency improved slightly, while a considerable number (43%) felt it improved moderately. Only a small number (11%) felt a significant improvement. This suggests the trial on the Chairman's Bao website was effective for most participants, with slight to moderate improvements being the most common. However, given that improvement was not perceived as significant by any of the participants, there might be room for enhancing the website's effectiveness to achieve more significant improvements.

The trial also had a positive impact on participants' confidence, with most feeling somewhat more confident in their reading skills after the trial. Most participants (71%) felt somewhat confident after the trial, a few participants (11%) felt very confident, and a smaller number (18%) remained neutral. Overall, this reflects a positive perception of the tool's ability to support their learning.

According to Zhang et al. (2023), technology-assisted teaching has become increasingly prevalent and influential in language instruction, including the teaching of Chinese characters to non-native speakers (p. 3). Their study highlights the positive impacts of technology on character acquisition, offering several benefits

such as providing multimedia resources, interactive exercises, and online platforms for language practice and assessment. These findings reinforce the importance of incorporating technology into language teaching, demonstrating its effectiveness in enhancing learners' learning experiences and outcomes.

This present study aligns with Zhang et al.'s findings by displaying how specific features of the Chairman's Bao website contributed to participants' improvement and confidence. Data suggested that there are many features on the website that contributed to the participants' level of improvement and their increase in confidence. The variety of reading materials and the website's vocabulary and grammar explanations received 86% of responses each, indicating their high value to the participants. Additionally, the audio recordings feature indicated by 71% of respondents, played a significant role in improving reading skills, particularly in terms of matching sounds to characters. This corroborates the benefits of technology-assisted teaching as outlined by Zhang et al., emphasizing the effectiveness of incorporating multimedia resources and interactive elements into language learning platforms.

The majority of the participants in this study were satisfied with the Chairman's Bao, with a significant number expressing either being very satisfied (43%) or somewhat satisfied (50%). This suggests that the platform met the expectations and needs of most users. The high level of satisfaction also implies that Chairman's Bao provides a beneficial and satisfactory learning experience for Mandarin Chinese language learners. This is corroborated by the previously mentioned improvements in reading proficiency and confidence.

Data showed a marked improvement in how learners perceived their reading skills after using the website. Most participants (71%) rated their proficiency as either 3 or 4, indicating a gradual shift towards moderate to high perceived proficiency levels. This is a notable improvement from previous ratings, where no one felt highly proficient reading in general and without the use of Pinyin.

Fig. 2. Line chart showing a comparison of participants' perception of their reading proficiency in Mandarin Chinese pre- and post-trial use of the Chairman's Bao platform. The highest rating is 5, while the lowest is 1.

Interestingly, the participants who did not complete some of the articles registered changes in their confidence levels, albeit minimal. For instance, uwistudent19 rated their overall proficiency as 2 in both pre- and post-surveys and felt "somewhat" confident in their ability to read Mandarin Chinese texts after completing the online reading platform, noting their proficiency had changed "slightly." Similarly, uwistudent27 maintained a proficiency rating of 2 and also felt "somewhat" confident, reporting a "slight" improvement. On the other hand, uwistudent26, who rated their proficiency as a rating of 3 in both surveys, felt "moderately" confident in their reading ability and noted a "slight" change in proficiency. This lack of significant improvement suggests a potential correlation between completion rates and shifts in confidence levels, indicating that fully engaging with the reading materials may be necessary for perceivable progress in proficiency.

Participants provided feedback on the reasons for their new ratings. Based on this, several key themes that were identified explain the new proficiency ratings and perceived improvements:

Table 4 - Table showing codes and themes explaining the new proficiency rating post-trial using the Chairman Bao website

Codes	Themes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent practice using the website • Introduction to new vocabulary • Introduction to grammatical structures • Variety of articles • Increased familiarity with repeated characters 	Exposure to the language through practice
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great tool for review. • Each article had a vocabulary list. 	Support and tools on website
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercises became easier • More comfort while reading in characters • More confidence while reading. • Improvement in reading speed. 	Confidence and perception

Firstly, exposure to the language through practice was frequently mentioned. For instance, one participant noted, *"This experience has introduced me to various different vocabulary, and grammatical structures, which I previously did not have the knowledge of"*. Another aspect of this theme is the variety of articles, as another participant highlighted, *"The passages were very interesting, and I learnt a lot of new vocabulary and grammar"*. Frequent practice with the website was also emphasized, with a participant stating, *"I was able to practice more and therefore become more comfortable with Mandarin Chinese reading."* Another participant expressed similar sentiments by stating *"I think the program is a fantastic way to reinforce grammar and vocabulary for each level. You see the grammar points repeat pretty often in different scenarios so it's great for learning"*.

Secondly, the availability of support and tools on the website was crucial. Several participants appreciated the vocabulary lists provided, and others acknowledged the website as a great tool for review. One participant expressed, *"The pure level of interactivity was highly likeable and the ability to see your grade at the end of each allows one to more easily assess their current knowledge and application level,"* indicating that the website's built-in features effectively complemented their efforts to improve their reading skills. Lastly, improvements in confidence and perception were significant. Participants noted that the exercises became easier and that they felt more comfortable while reading characters. Increased confidence while reading and improvement in reading speed were also common, as one participant mentioned, *"I am now able to identify and read characters at a faster pace than I did before starting"*. These insights collectively explain the positive shift in the participants' proficiency ratings and their overall confidence in reading Mandarin Chinese.

Participants were also given a character recognition exercise in which they must identify words from the vocabulary lists of the ten articles. The exercise was divided into four vocabulary sets, with each set containing five words in Chinese characters. When comparing the above-mentioned qualitative insights to the data on character recognition rates from these vocabulary sets, there is a noticeable improvement. For instance, in Set 1, most participants recognized at least 3 or 4 characters, and in Set 3, most participants recognized 3 or 4 characters, with some recognizing all 5. This is an improvement from the pre-trial reading comprehension exercise, where the test contained no Pinyin, yet much of the sample performed remarkably well. The post-trial data suggests that the participants' proficiency in recognizing characters has continued to develop, with many now able to identify and read characters more effectively. This progression aligns with their feedback, highlighting how the exposure to varied vocabulary, grammatical structures, and engaging reading materials on the Chairman's Bao website has contributed to their improved proficiency and confidence in reading Mandarin Chinese.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study explored how ICT tools can improve Mandarin Chinese reading proficiency among adult native English-speaking learners in Trinidad and Tobago. Using the Chairman's Bao website, designed for Mandarin reading practice, participants completed a 14-day trial alongside two surveys. The results demonstrated a positive impact of ICT on reading proficiency and confidence, with most participants reporting improvements in their ability to read Chinese characters. Additionally, participants highlighted the effectiveness of multimedia resources like audio recordings and interactive text in enhancing engagement and retention. However, the study noted limitations such as the small sample size, gender imbalance, and the relatively short trial period, which may affect the generalizability of the findings.

The research suggests several avenues for future exploration, including studying the long-term impact of ICT tools like the Chairman's Bao on reading proficiency, examining strategies to reduce learners' reliance on Pinyin, and conducting a comparative analysis of different ICT tools used in Mandarin learning. By investigating these areas, educators and researchers can better understand how to integrate technology into language instruction, offering tailored solutions to enhance learners' reading skills and confidence in Mandarin Chinese.

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